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The Study on Guerrilla Marketing with Ad Creativity Affects Word of Mouth of Consumers.

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Abstract

This study examines the impact of guerrilla marketing tools, supported by ad creativity, on consumer word-of-mouth. The objective is to explore the role of sensation marketing, characterized by one-time surprise effects, in generating word-of-mouth and leveraging creative advertising media. The study adopts a quantitative approach, employing a closed-ended questionnaire technique to collect data from 202 respondents. The questionnaire was filled out cross-sectionally by individuals regularly exposed to various forms of advertisements. Hypothesis tests were conducted using the Linear and Hierarchical Regression method in SPSS20.0. The findings confirm the influence of guerrilla sensation on word-of-mouth, with ad creativity mediating the relationship between guerrilla sensation and word-of-mouth. Additionally, the study demonstrates the impact of ad creativity on word-of-mouth. In conclusion, the study suggests that surprise and humor, combined with a clear message, emotionally engage consumers, leading to attention, resistance, and memorization of guerrilla marketing messages. This approach, facilitated by creative advertising media and incorporating novelty and relevance elements, enhances curiosity and promotes effective word-of-mouth, aiding companies in spreading their message. The study also highlights the potential positive or negative impact of word-of-mouth on a company's reputation. Considering ethical considerations in advertising presentation and the digital media revolution, the concept of sensation marketing can be adapted to digital marketing platforms.

Keywords: Guerrilla Marketing, Advertisements, Creativity, Word of mouth, Sensation Marketing

Introduction

In the contemporary digital age, businesses allocate significant budgets to marketing endeavors. (Jankoska, 2015); The concept of guerrilla marketing emerges as a suggestion when seeking innovative and distinctive techniques for promoting a product (Ay & Canan, 2010). The adoption of unconventional methods to market products appears to be gaining popularity among competing companies (Soomro, 2021). "Ads which being fancy innovative, creative, unusual, original, provoking all belong to guerrilla marketing" (Hoffmann & hutter, 2011). It is crucial for Guerrilla Marketing to effectively convey the branding campaign's message to the intended audience, regardless of their location, to generate a lasting brand experience and promote word-of-mouth within the desired target demographic (Kotler. P. & Armstrong, 2004). A lot of businesses have executed guerrilla marketing techniques around the globe (Jung, 2017). These brands include Nestle, Lipton, Ray-Ban, and Ponds, which exploit public spaces (such as posters and bus stops) to attract customers. A good guerrilla marketing campaign attracts customers' attention while also communicating the marketing message (Hatch, 2005). Kotler emphasized that there are various methods available to engage with customers, such as direct marketing, public relations, personal selling, sales promotions, and advertising. However, one contemporary approach stands out as guerrilla marketing communication, which involves implementing innovative ideas. (Kotler. P. & Armstrong, 2004). Marketing strategies should align with the brand's objectives, requiring marketers to exhibit creativity and explore innovative promotional approaches. These initiatives are typically designed to capture the target audience's attention through various means, including direct marketing, public relations, and unconventional advertising methods. (Jankoska, 2015). Guerrilla marketing enables companies to foster marketing entrepreneurship and achieve optimal outcomes within limited resources (Mahmooditavana, Somi, & Baghbaniyazdi, 2014).

According to (Naeem Akhtar, 2016), guerrilla marketing refers to an unconventional advertising technique utilized to effectively establish the business performance of products or services while minimizing business expenses. Drawing a distinct and exact distinction among the numerous tools of guerrilla marketing is a challenging task. However, it is important to note that these individual instruments complement each other and collectively contribute to the genuine impact of guerrilla marketing. (Jung, 2017). Changes in markets, communications, and consumers have created new marketing opportunities. "Knowing the most essential norms of communication is advantageous because it allows one to transgress them more consciously (Nufer, 2021). With time, the concept changes from a competitor-oriented strategy to a customer-oriented one (Hayes, L., G., & Applequist, 2019).In what way

does the concept of guerrilla marketing develop into a marketing conflict but need to know whether the tactic has an impact on word of mouth?

Aim of the Study

This research aims to find out the significant role of guerrilla marketing surprise and diffusion effects on ad creativity, and word-of-mouth generation. The established connection is underpinned by theoretical frameworks, with the independent variable being guerrilla sensation influencing the dependent variable, word of mouth. Simultaneously, ad creativity assumes a mediating role in the relationship between guerrilla sensation and word of mouth. The study specifically selected three variables: guerrilla sensation, denoting the singular surprise impact, emotional arousal, flexibility, and a humorous approach to astonishing people by presenting an advertisement in an unexpected location. (Saira & Samreen, 2015), and by unexpected means (Baltes & Leibing, 2008). Consumers exhibit heightened interest in the message because of the unexpected impact of extraordinary guerrilla actions. (Hutter & Hoffmann, 2014). The second variable is Ad creativity. In the literature, ad creativity has been defined in two basic ways. Divergence, according to some studies, is what determines ad inventiveness (Till & Daniel, 2005). The degree to which an advertisement incorporates features that are unique, distinct, or uncommon is referred to as divergence (Smith & Xiaoqing, 2004). Originality, flexibility, elaboration, synthesis, and aesthetic value were identified as five elements that may account for how divergence could be attained in advertising (Smith, Chen, & Yang, 2008). The third variable is Word-of-Mouth refers to informal verbal communication that takes place either in person, face-to-face, or through electronic means of communication (Ferguson, 2008). It involves the exchange of formal and informal gestures and the flow of communication, where consumers engage in discussions about their post-purchase experiences for noncommercial reasons. (Isabelle & Line, 2010). The *research gap* identified in this study is what effects guerrilla sensation tactics generate on word of mouth and Ad creativity when it mediates the relation of ad creativity and word of mouth.

Literature Review

Guerrilla marketing takes a brand message and exposes it to the target audience unexpectedly and intimately. (Margolis, 2008) It may also be considered a form of clickbait, rumors, or hidden marketing because the notion involves promoting a non-traditional way that is supposed to reach a large number of people with few budgets (Hoffmann & hutter, 2011). The researchers elaborate that this form of advertisement surprises the public or pedestrians with an action that is beyond expectation (Vikas & Sania, 2014). Emotional Arousal refers to the cognitive and physiological processes that take place in the brain and nervous system (Richins, 1997). It involves the expression of emotions, the observable patterns of facial expressions, bodily movements, and the subjective experience of pleasantness, leading to

heightened emotional states in individuals. (Dinh Duc & Mai Ngoc, 2015). Arousal and more complex knowledge acquisition in the consumers are also caused by surprise. Put simply, when there is a discrepancy between an advertisement and the customer's expectations, it prompts them to scrutinize the ad more attentively. (Halkias & Kokkinaki, 2014). The consumer does not expect that the product will be advertised in that way and they direct their attention to the message (Snelders & P. Hekkert, 1999). These marketing techniques try to surprise their consumer by insertion ads in strange places (Hutter & Hoffmann, 2014). Customers' attention must be captured before they are interested in the goods, which is also the major purpose of marketers Humor in commercials is also linked to a more favorable attitude about the ads and companies, as well as an increase in buy intent (Eisend, 2011). Humor in a commercial is determined by the characteristics of the stimuli and is achieved through the use of comedy devices, which can be seen as the specific techniques employed to create a humorous effect in the advertisement. (Sternthal & C. S., 1973). One more important aspect to consider is the clarity of the message (Nunthipatprueksa, 2017). The tactics of guerrilla marketing are unusual, the conformation of intent must be reflected through the activity. The capacity of an individual to grasp a message is referred to as message clarity. The more complex a communication is, the greater the cognitive effort required by the audience to comprehend it. (Hafer, Reynolds, & Obertynski, 1996). Sensation marketing initiatives are one-time events that cannot be repeated. The goal is to surprise and fascinate customers, resulting in a "wow" or "aha" reaction. "Guerrilla sensation" and "ambient stunt" are phrases used to describe uncommon and stunning special events (Jäckel, 2007).

Unconventional marketing communication is exemplified by creative media advertising. Guerrilla marketing is a term used to describe nontraditional marketing communications (Saucet & Cova, 2014). The following characteristics set creative media advertising apart from other sorts of unusual marketing communications: It reinforces the brand's message and was previously not regarded as a typical medium for advertising. Ad Creativity has three components novelty, meaningfulness, and connectedness (Ang & Low, 2000). The term "novelty" refers to a creative concept. A meaningful ad has adequate meaning and accurately conveys what the marketer intended. When the notion of advertising is not defined, advertising innovation suffers. The premise of advertising should be clear for the message to be conveyed effectively. (Robert E., Jiemiao, & Xiaojing, 2008). The Message Design: Creativity and Credibility is an important tool in marketing (J., 1993). In advertising, creative approaches are more likely to leave a lasting impression and remain in the audience's memory. Research has indicated that a creative message captures greater attention and cultivates a positive attitude toward the promoted product. (Taylor, Jeffrey, & David, 2011). (Jankoska, 2015) have conducted studies to investigate the impact of creative advertisements on consumer behavior and attitudes. The findings revealed that companies that invested in highly creative

advertising campaigns experienced a significant increase in brand sales. Additionally, surprise, often considered a fundamental emotion, can be seen as a state that primes the body and mind to explore and gain knowledge about the unknown. Surprise is defined by (Nufer, 2021) as a combination of physiological, behavioral, and subjective responses. When individuals encounter unexpected stimuli, their reaction time increases, their attention becomes fixated on the unexpected stimulus, and they consciously experience a sense of surprise. Consequently, the use of creative media can elicit heightened cognitive responses. (Saucet & Cova, 2014). (Turki & Sayadi, 2016) suggesting that a powerful advertising campaign possesses the capability to shape consumer perceptions. The credibility of a brand is established by its capacity to fulfill the commitments it makes to consumers. (Castillo, Mendoza, & dan Poblete, 2013). Typical advertising strategies are applied in street marketing but in unorthodox ways and places, such as on benches, zebra crossings, and electric poles. The component of originality is used to assess the reaction and efficacy of street marketing. (Hoffmann & hutter, 2011). Compared to traditional marketing, a guerrilla marketing campaign is more captivating and captures consumers' attention. The use of a creative medium in advertising is unconventional for consumers, which can evoke a sense of surprise (Halkias & Kokkinaki, 2014).

There is empirical evidence that surprise is one of the driving factors of spread through (electronic) WOM when it comes to behavioral reactions (Berger & Milkman, 2012). This might be related to selective self-improvement concerns. People are more willing to share what they think will make them seem interesting to others. Guerrilla marketing is known for eliciting feelings of surprise (Hutter & Hoffmann, 2011) The creative media will enhance the cognitive assessment to drive the value of the ad (Dahlén, Granlund, & M., 2009b) p. 156). A person who enjoys using a product will undoubtedly share their experience in a social circle and will emotionally persuade the customer to purchase it (Berger & Iyengar, 2013).

Guerrilla marketing refers to a promotional strategy that utilizes unique environments and a strong word-of-mouth (WOM) campaign to promote and distribute products to the market. (Baltes & Leibing, 2008) Credibility has a link with WOM's willingness to use information if they believe it is trustworthy (Castillo, Mendoza, & dan Poblete, 2013). The most efficient technique to advertise is WOM communication, in which an individual who has experienced the product passes on the proper knowledge to others, and the process continues (Wu & Wang, 2011); (Hoffmann & hutter, 2011). In other words, the customer will spread the message to others since it has inspired or gratified them. Viral marketing and Buzz marketing are two marketing instruments that are used to disseminate a message (Baltes & Leibing, 2008). According to (Ferguson, 2008), word of mouth is the most powerful means of generating excitement and disseminating information globally, leading to the viral spread of news. Celebrity endorsements often assist marketers in promoting a product and reaching a wide-ranging

audience. (MM & Shakeel, 2011). The message must be stimulated in a goal-oriented and cost-effective manner (Hutter & Hoffmann, 2011) The word-of-mouth strategy allows consumers to talk about a company's product and begin offering evaluations, writing, and expressing their experiences to those in their immediate vicinity (Mahmooditavana, Somi, & Baghbaniyazdi, 2014). Recent studies examining the effectiveness of innovative media choices have provided empirical evidence that utilizing creative advertising mediums can result in stronger brand associations and longer-lasting impact compared to traditional advertising approaches (Nufer, 2021). Relevance, which is a component of advertising creativity, has been proven to boost advertising effectiveness time and time again (Jung, 2017). Creative ads attract greater attention, resulting in more favorable sentiments about advertisements and businesses (Sweetser, Ahn, Golan, & Hochman, 2016), as well as an increase in WOM (Hayes, L., G., & Applequist, 2019). Research evidence supports that ads that have creativity and unexpected effects will influence customer perception in deciding attitudes toward the ad as well as its believability (Hutter & Hoffmann, 2014). If the ad succeeds in grabbing a favorable consumer attitude, the message received by the customer will influence shopper behavior (Tam & Khuong N., 2015) The above theoretical support drives the hypothesis of the study

H1: Guerrilla sensation activities affect the Word of Mouth of consumers.

H2: Guerrilla sensation activities affect Ad Creativity.

H3 Creativity affects the Word of Mouth of consumers.

H4: Ad Creativity mediates the relation between the Guerrilla sensation activities and word of mouth of consumers.

Figure1: Theoretical Framework

Research Design

A quantitative technique was used to perform the research because the variables are fully developed. The close-ended questionnaire approach is used to collect data and design it on a Google form. The unit of analysis for the study has a shopping experience. The questionnaire is filled out in a cross-sectional approach and is collected from persons who have been routinely exposed to any method and any type of advertisement. The proposed hypothesis is tested by the Linear Regression method and mediation analysis is performed by Hierarchical Regression on SPSS.

Measure

Existing scale items for suggested variables were included since the variables were completely established. Responses were gathered on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 5=Strongly Agree to 1=Strongly Disagree.

Guerrilla Sensation: The variable Guerrilla Sensation is measured by 4 characteristics supported by (Dinh Duc & Mai Ngoc, 2015) i.e. 3 items of Emotional Aurosal, 2 items of Clarity, 1 item of Humour, and 1 item of Surprise. A total of 7 items were added. The sample items from the scale are "It is easy to understand Ad message", and "The claims made in the ad are sometimes memorable."

Ad Creativity: The ad creativity was measured by items taken from (Smith, Chen, & Yang, 2008). The items related to ad divergence were added to it. A total of 8 items were added 2 items of resistance, 2 items of attention, 2 items of memorable, and 2 items of curiosity. The sample items from the scale are "The ad would stand out in a group of ads", and "The caused me to consider views different from my own"

Word of Mouth: Word of mouth was measured by 10 item scale (Isabelle & Line, 2010) . 2 items of positive valence word of mouth, 2 items of Negative valence word of mouth, The 3 items for Word of mouth content were added and 3 items of Word of Mouth intensity is added. The sample items from the scale are "I discuss the variety of the products offered", "I mostly rely on positive comments on social websites", and "I strongly recommend people to buy products of my experienced company."

Sampling and Data Collection

The Population of the study is the people living in Lahore Pakistan who have exposure to shopping. The sample of the respondents was above 18 years old with a brand experience of shopping from the malls and prominent markets of Lahore, A total of 202 responses were collected. After removing the outlier 196 were left and the test was conducted on the 196 respondents. The participants fell in the age range of above 16 with and household income of a minimum of 18,000/-, both male and female gender was added. The demographic analysis shows that out of 196 respondents, 136 (i.e. 69.4 percent) were male respondents and 60 (i.e. 30.6 percent) were female respondents. Analysis shows that most of the respondents i.e. (69.4 percent) of respondents were in the age range of 21-30 and most of the respondent's household income was >150,000 (i.e.28.9 percent). Table 1 shows all reporting of demographic Analysis

Table: Demographical Characteristics of Respondents

	Demographics	N	%
Age	16-20	25	12.8
	21-30	136	69.4
	31-40	20	10.2
	41-50	11	5.6
	>50	4	2.0

Gender	Male	136	69.4
	Female	60	30.6
Household Income	25000 -40000/-	34	17.3
	41000-80,000	32	16.3
	81000-110,000	37	18.9
	110,000-150,000	37	18.9
	Above 150,000	56	28.9

Results

The results are computed on the SPSS. To make the data best fit for analysis. The researcher has performed two tests on the data. The Missing Value and Outliers were performed and no missing values were found in the data. The 4 outliers were identified by the stem and leaf method and were removed successfully. The data was normality distributed which is checked by skewness and kurtosis test, stating that the data referring to (Byrne, 2010) lie between the range of ± 1 for Skewness and ± 3 for Kurtosis.

Correlation and Reliability Analysis

The mean and standard deviation of the observed variables, Guerrilla Sensation, Ad creativity, and word of mouth. The mean of guerrilla sensation was 3.54 and the standard deviation was 0.62. The mean of ad creativity was 3.34 and the standard deviation was 0.67. The mean of word of mouth was 3.74 and the standard deviation was 0.58 as shown in Table 2. The correlation analysis shows that guerrilla sensation is positively related to ad creativity ($r=0.35, p<0.01$) and word of mouth ($r=0.10, p<0.01$), and ad creativity is positively related to word of mouth ($r=0.21, p<0.01$). The good Cronbach alpha (α) value according to (Hair, Black, & Babin, 2006) is ≥ 0.07 is referred to be good and acceptable, so according to it all scales are reliable, and the guerrilla sensation is reported to be 0.71, ad creativity to 0.84, and word of mouth 0.80.

Table2: Correlation Analysis

Variables	1	2	3	Mean	S.D.	A
1. GS	1			3.54	0.62	0.71
2. AC	0.35**	1		3.34	0.67	0.84
3. WOM	0.10**	0.21**	1	3.74	0.58	0.80

Notes: GS=Guerrilla Sensation, AC=Ad Creativity, WOM=Word of Mouth, S.D.=Standard Deviation α =Cronbach Alpha

Hypothesis Tests

The three hypotheses were proposed in a study that was to find the impact of guerrilla sensation on ad creativity and word of mouth and the impact of ad creativity on word of mouth. The regression analysis shows that the guerrilla sensation has a significant impact the word of mouth ($\beta=0.15, p<0.05$) and ad creativity ($\beta=0.56, p<0.01$). This shows that guerrilla sensation has impacted more on ad creativity than

word of mouth. The third hypothesis also shows that Ad creativity has a significant impact on Word of Mouth ($\beta=0.13$, $p<0.05$) as reported in Table 3

Table 3: Regression Analysis

Hypothesis	β	R^2	P	Result
GS \rightarrow WOM	0.15	0.05	0.02	Accepted
GS \rightarrow AC	0.56	0.18	0.00	Accepted
AC \rightarrow WOM	0.13	0.06	0.01	Accepted

Notes: GS=Guerrilla Sensation, AC=Ad Creativity, WOM=Word of Mouth

Mediation Analysis

The fourth hypothesis of the study is to examine the mediation effect of ad creativity on the relation between guerrilla sensation and word of mouth through a three-step hierarchical regression method. In the first step, all the demographic characteristics (gender, age, household income) were added to control their effects. In the second step independent variable, the guerrilla sensation was added and in the third step mediating variable ad creativity was added and noted their significant impact. In the first step, the r square value was 0.05, in the second model r square value was 0.10 and it showed a change of 0.16, in the third model r square value was 0.13 and it was observed that it showed a change of 0.23 in the value of r square as compared to model 2 value. Guerrilla sensation shows a significant impact on word of mouth ($\beta=0.16$, $p<0.05$) by putting demographic characteristics constant. In the third step, ad creativity showed a significant impact ($\beta=0.10$, $p<0.05$). The value of guerrilla sensation changes to insignificant ($\beta=0.13$, $p>0.05$) which shows the full mediation because the β coefficient value of the independent variable guerrilla sensation changes to insignificant from significant. It supports the fourth hypothesis of the study that ad creativity fully mediates the relation between guerrilla sensation and word of mouth.

Table: Hierarchical Regression for Mediation

Variables	M1(β)	M2(β)	M3 (β)
Control Variable			
Age	-0.001	-0.01	-0.03
Gender	0.18*	0.20*	0.19*
HH income	0.009	0.01	0.02
R^2	0.05		
Independent Variable			
GS		0.16*	0.13
R^2		0.10	
ΔR		0.16	
Mediating Variable			

AC	0.10*
R^2	0.13
ΔR	0.23

Conclusion

Finding the influence of guerrilla marketing's surprise effect on consumer word-of-mouth in the context of creative advertising is the study's primary goal. The study establishes a correlation between the three variables under investigation. The primary objective is to examine how the creative presentation of advertisements, specifically through sensation marketing, affects the development of word-of-mouth. The variables considered are guerrilla sensation (independent variable), word of mouth (dependent variable), and ad creativity (mediating variable). The hypothesis suggests that guerrilla sensation influences both word of mouth and ad creativity, while ad creativity impacts word of mouth. The results indicate a significant positive impact of guerrilla sensation on word of mouth ($\beta=0.15$, $p<0.05$), as well as on ad creativity ($\beta=0.56$, $p<0.01$). In simple, the results indicate that the guerrilla sensation impacts the way the ad is presented to the consumer, and if it is presented with surprise and humor elements with clarity that pitch the emotional stigma in the consumer, and consumer will attract, resist, pay attention will memorize the message and when target audience got an exposure they can generate the word of mouth about the advertising message, they will generate a positive or negative feeling and will discuss and recommend the brand/company in social circle. The fourth hypothesis is also supported and concludes that ad creativity fully mediates the relation between guerrilla sensation and word of mouth, evidence that ad creativity has an impact on the relation. It is elaborated as an unattractive, simple ad that can't help to stick a one-time surprise effect of sensation marketing in the mind of the consumer. The theoretical implication of a study is a review of the consumer behavior theory of reasoned action and planned behavior, psychological and cognitive approach, and emotional arousal towards ads that are displayed in an unconventional place. Various tactics, such as print media, electronic platforms, and celebrity endorsements, are commonly employed by many companies. Celebrity endorsements are particularly effective in reaching a large audience and creating a significant impact, but they often require substantial budgets that may only be affordable for big brands. However, for small startups aiming to advertise their services, utilizing guerrilla marketing techniques can allow them to achieve ambitious goals with limited budgets. The beauty of this smart approach lies in its flexibility compared to other marketing strategies, as it enables businesses to connect with their target audience using simple yet effective techniques. By designing messages specifically tailored to reach the desired audience, costs are reduced, making it an ideal option for firms operating on smaller marketing budgets. If successful, the impact can be tremendous, resulting in improved brand recall and positioning. This approach signifies a shift from a competitor-focused mindset to a customer-focused one. The emergence of guerrilla marketing stemmed from marketing conflicts and challenges. Guerrilla marketing is employed by the business to help it cultivate marketing entrepreneurship and get the most out of its scarce resources. I ought to think about some moral concerns which limit my study findings. The chosen material for advertising should be appropriate and implemented appropriately. Only the right message should be reflected in the visuals and the material. Playing the game of double meanings must be avoided. Deceptive and false advertisements could result in incorrect judgments. Avoid making overt assertions about how great your product is or making direct

connections to your rival. Advertising content should avoid eliciting intense emotions such as anger. Marketers are increasingly exploring unconventional spaces like restrooms, bridges, ceilings, public walls, or large gatherings, where consumers are least likely to anticipate encountering ads. Notably, the most effective guerrilla technique in the current landscape is viral and buzz marketing. Leveraging social media as a broad platform for product promotion is crucial, as people frequently use it to share experiences and information, facilitating extensive dissemination. The proliferation of brand discussions and consumer feedback on social media results in enduring positive publicity, aiding businesses in building a substantial customer base. In Ambient marketing, the emphasis is not solely on the concept but on the advertising space itself. Guerrilla Sensation operates on a similar principle to ambient marketing but is applied selectively to a very limited number of events and activities. In the digital era, marketers may not frequently prioritize the use of the sensation marketing technique. The study introduces novel research avenues concerning how word-of-mouth generation, whether positive or negative, influences the reputation of the company. The sensation marketing concept will get more polished if it is implemented in digital media marketing. The ideas of advertising in a unique way can be added to a digital marketing campaign by keeping the main purpose of guerrilla marketing alive and blending the concept of out-of-home advertising with digital media. Future studies must be to implement the guerrilla sensation technique in digital media campaigns.

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